

The European Health Data Space

Secure Processing Environments

SANTE C1

EHDS in a Nutshell – what is it about?

1. Primary use = use of data for the delivery of healthcare
 - Improving patients' access to their health data;
 - Ensuring seamless exchanges for continuity of healthcare.
2. Secondary use = use of data for research and public interest purposes
 - Making data available for research, policy-making etc. in a safe and secure way.
3. Requirements for electronic health record (EHR) systems
 - Creating a single market for electronic health records systems, supporting both primary and secondary use.

Data User Journey

Data discovery

What health data exists to support my research?

Permit application

Can I use this data for my research project?

Data preparation

Issue permit and make data ready for use, ensuring data quality and privacy.

Data provision

Give access to **Secure Processing Environment**

Data use

Analyse and process data

Results output

Publish of results, ensuring privacy and verifiability

Cross-border secondary use infrastructure

HealthData @EU

 Central support services provided by EC

 NCP2U - National Contact Point for Secondary Use
EUCP2U - European Contact Point for Secondary Use

 Data access services

 CAT National dataset/metadata catalogue

 DAA Data Access Application Management system

 SPE Secure Processing Environments

 Local services provided by/to local partners

National context

Secure Processing Environment

- ‘secure processing environment’ means the **physical or virtual environment** and organisational means to ensure compliance with Union law, such as Regulation (EU) 2016/679, in particular with regard to data subjects’ rights, intellectual property rights, and commercial and statistical confidentiality, integrity and accessibility, as well as with applicable national law, and to allow the entity providing the secure processing environment **to determine and supervise all data processing actions, including the display, storage, download and export of data and the calculation of derivative data through computational algorithms.** (Ref. Regulation (EU) 2022/868)

Secure Processing Environment – EHDS regulation

- Health data access bodies, trusted health data holders and the Union health data access service shall store and process personal electronic health data in the Union when performing **pseudonymisation, anonymisation and any other personal data processing operations**, through secure processing environments (SPEs).
- **Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs) shall provide access to electronic health data, corresponding to a data permit**, only through an **EHDS-compliant SPE** (*Art. 57*). The SPE doesn't need to be hosted by the HDAB itself.
- There will be a **market of SPEs**. They need to **comply with the technical and organizational measures and security** and interoperability requirements.
- HDABs will ensure that **Health Data Holders upload the data corresponding to a permit in the right format in the SPE**.
- **SPEs will be audited**, including by third parties, the user's processing of data within the SPE and the compliance of the SPE with the technical specifications and security measures.
- Only **users mentioned in the data permit** will be **authorised** to access and process data in the SPE, no other users will be able to access it. (*Art. 61*)
- The health data user **can bring datasets** that they hold already. However, there will be a **check-in gate** to ensure what is being brought inside is secure and is corresponding to the description provided in the permit. (*Art. 67(f)*)
- The SPE will need to contain the **tools and computing resources** requested by the user at the application phase. (*Art. 67(i)*)
- The electronic **health data within the SPE shall be deleted within six months of the expiry of the data permit** (10 years + 10 years + 6 months). At the request of the health data user, the formula for the creation of the requested dataset may be stored by the health data access body. (*Art. 68*)

Security measures

- **Article 73** of the regulation specifies the security, organizational and technical specifications of the EHDS-compliant SPEs. This article will be complemented by the technical specifications resulting from the TEHDAS2 Joint Action which will feed into the implementing act.
 - HDABs have to **minimise the risk of unauthorised reading**, copying, modification or removal of electronic health data hosted in the SPE through state-of-the-art technical and organisational measures;
 - Keeping **of identifiable logs** of access to and activities in the SPE for the period necessary to verify and audit all processing operations in that environment; logs of access shall be kept for at least one year;
 - Health data access bodies shall review the electronic health data included in a download request to ensure that health data users are only able **to download nonpersonal electronic health data, including electronic health data in an anonymised statistical format**, from the SPE → check-out gate.

TEHDAS2 guidelines and TechSpecs

- **Implementing act** should state the technical, organisational, information security, confidentiality, data protection and interoperability requirements for the SPEs. **By spring 2027.**
- TEHDAS2 is developing **the technical specifications** that will feed into this implementing act. First draft and public consultation will be Sept-Oct 2025.
- Guideline for users of SPEs already under public consultation.
 - “Guideline on how to use data in a secure processing environment”
 - Public consultation will be open until 26th of February 2025

Community of Practice and Capacity Building

- Direct Grants to Member States to establish their HDAB
- Community of Practice: Subgroup 3 on Secure Processing Environments, alignment and sharing of best practices.
- Capacity Building team is developing training material on, among others, secure processing environments.

EC Secure Processing Environment (EC SPE)

- An SPE **provided by the Commission to analyse pseudonymised health data** coming from Union institutions, bodies offices or agencies.
- An SPE that will be provided to member state' HDABs in case of **multi-country application requests**.
- Where requested by **two or more national contact points for secondary use, the Commission may provide an SPE.** (*Art. 75 §9*)
- Needs to be able **to receive sensitive health datasets from different data holders**, from different member states, authorised participants and **linked to different permits**.
- Needs **to comply with the technical and organisational measures, security and interoperability** requirements determined in the **EHDS regulation**.

EHDS2 – Roadmap

EHDS – Overall timeline for application

Thank you!